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FEATURES OF CLINICAL COURSE, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF VIRAL PNEUMONIA IN YOUNG CHILDREN

Abstract.

Pneumonia is a serious medical problem with a high morbidity rate. Among hospitalized children with acute bronchopulmonary diseases, the proportion of pneumonia patients under the age of 1 is 25-30%, and among children aged 1-5 years - 50%. Mortality from pneumonia in different regions of Ukraine ranges from 1.5 to 6.0 per 10,000 children, which is reflected in the mortality structure of children in the first year of life, as respiratory diseases account for 3-5% of it. It should be noted that this figure is much higher in the pediatric population than in adults.

***Objective:** based on the generalization of modern literature data, to present clinical and paraclinical features and treatment of pneumonia caused by common viral pathogens in preschool children.*

Etiology and pathogenesis

Viruses cause pneumonia in 14-35% of cases. Pneumonia of viral etiology most often occurs in children under 5 years of age. MS virus is the most common cause of pneumonia in children under 3 years of age. In younger age groups, parainfluenza, influenza, and adenoviruses can be the etiologic factor. A significant number of pneumonia cases are caused by mixed infection (8-40%). The occurrence, development, course and consequences of pneumonia depend on the virulent properties of the pathogen and the degree of the macroorganism's immune response to the infection.

The development of viral pneumonia is based on interstitial inflammation. The penetration of viruses into the alveoli leads to their destruction and loss of surfactant. Pathologic hyperhydration of the lung interstitium develops, which prevents the diffusion of gases in the lungs. There is a violation of the diffusion properties of the alveolar-capillary membrane, which leads to an increase in the difference between the partial pressure in the alveolar gas and its tension in the end part of the pulmonary capillaries, a disorder of the ventilation-perfusion ratio and arterial hypoxemia. [1]

Features of the clinical course

Pneumonia caused by adenovirus. Adenovirus is tropic not only to the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract, but also to lymphoid tissue (lymph nodes). Typical clinical manifestations of pneumonia are fever above 39°C, which lasts up to 8 days. The presence of both dry and wet cough, rhinitis, sinusitis, and regional lymphadenitis is characteristic. Fatigue or muscle pain, neurological symptoms are not typical.

Pneumonia caused by influenza A and B viruses.

The incidence of pneumonia increases significantly in accordance with the epidemic season of influenza and acute respiratory viral infections (December - February). The disease is acute, with common clinical symp-

oms of influenza infection: sore throat, rhinitis, fatigue, muscle pain, headache, fever (febrile body temperature for 2.5-6 days), and a logical cough. Respiratory manifestations (shortness of breath, wheezing, decreased SaO₂ ≤ 95%) are rare.

Pneumonia caused by the parainfluenza virus. It occurs throughout the year, with a peak from October to April. The main clinical manifestations of this disease are cough with sputum production and rhinitis. There are no symptoms of intoxication, and the body temperature of most patients remains within normal limits. There are isolated cases of respiratory disorders.

Pneumonia caused by RSV. The disease peaks in early winter and spring. The main clinical manifestations of pneumonia are febrile fever for 2-5 days, cough with sputum, rhinitis, wheezing, shortness of breath. [2]

Features of the diagnosis of pneumonia of viral etiology

Chest radiography remains the standard for the standard diagnosis of pneumonia. X-ray examination does not allow to differentiate the type of viral pneumonia, but a negative radiograph excludes pneumonia. In recent years, lung ultrasonography has been widely used to diagnose pneumonia in children, which has demonstrated high sensitivity, specificity and reliability in detecting lung consolidation. Computed tomography should be considered in difficult situations when the results of radiography indicate the presence of nodular infiltrates, destruction, moderate and large effusions that require additional parameters. The main radiological sign of viral pneumonia on CT images was consolidation, which was detected in 88.9% of children with pneumonia caused by influenza A and B viruses, and in almost half of children with pneumonia caused by parainfluenza virus. Thus, the informative signs of visual examination are the presence of bilateral lung lesions in adenovirus pneumonia and consolidation in pneumonia caused by influenza A and B viruses.

Laboratory diagnostics: Rapid tests, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), serologic analysis. The PCR method allows to identify viruses in 80% of children with pneumonia and to determine the atypical flora. Given the risks of complications, invasive diagnostic methods (direct lung tissue sampling, bronchoscopy) are used in some cases in severe patients. In the main cohort of children, regardless of the type of viral pneumonia, the number of leukocytes remained in the range of $5.7-14.3 \times 10^9/L$, leukopenia with neutropenia was more typical for pneumonia caused by influenza A and B viruses. There were no significant differences between the indicators in children with viral pneumonia caused by RSV, parainfluenza virus and adenovirus. There are isolated cases of thrombocytopenia in viral pneumonia, regardless of the type of pathogen. [3,4]

Treatment

In case of pneumonia caused by influenza virus, targeted antiviral therapy with neuraminidase inhibitors (oseltamivir and zanamivir) is used.

When conducting targeted antiviral therapy, it should be borne in mind that:

- treatment should be started as early as possible: within 48 hours of the onset of the disease;
- before prescribing antiviral drugs, do not wait for laboratory confirmation of influenza, as this delays the start of therapy, and a negative rapid test does not refute the diagnosis of influenza;
- patients with severe or progressive disease should be prescribed antiviral drugs at a later date

Despite the fact that most preschool children with viral pneumonia have concomitant mycoplasma infection or bacterial complications, most of them require

antibiotic therapy. Macrolides (azithromycin, clarithromycin) are the first-line antibiotics in the treatment of mycoplasma pneumonia. [5,6]

Conclusions :

1. Thus, viral pneumonia remains one of the leading pathologies of childhood.
2. Based on the analysis of the paraclinical results of pneumonia screening, it can be argued that PCR testing helps in diagnosis and verification of the diagnosis.

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